

Maximizing the Reproductive Efficiency of Cattle: A Review Benefits of Sexual Puberty Induction in Heifers Through Hormonal Protocols

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Abstract:- The induction of puberty in cattle is of great value in maximizing reproductive efficiency with the aim of promoting greater financial and economic gains from livestock activity. Hormone treatment has been used worldwide in heifers as a way to improve reproductive efficiency. This work aims to present the different protocols used to induce puberty in heifers and the associated benefits for the cow as well as for the farm.

Keywords:- Puberty induction; Reproductive efficiency; Heifers.

I. INTRODUCTION

It is expected that by 2050, the world population will grow by more than a third, reaching more than 9 billion people and therefore the pressure for food production will increase by about 70% (Zhang et al., 2021). Livestock in general plays a key role in the production and supply of food of animal origin Waters-Bayer and Bayer, 1992; Nkadimeng *et al.*, 2021; Direito, 2022). Cattle production is fundamental in promoting food security as it provides protein of high biological value (meat and milk) (Mkize and Zishiri, 2021). In some African countries, such as Mozambique, cattle contribute to the fertilization of agricultural fields and is used for animal traction, thus increasing the income of the peasants, in addition to being used as dowries in weddings and traditional ceremonies (Herrero et al., 2013; Mutami, 2015; Direito, 2022; Nkadimeng et al., 2021; Mkize and Zishiri, 2021).

Given the importance of cattle due to the global pressure for food and its utilities in general, the need to ensure greater production and productivity in livestock farming and increase profits becomes clear. Thus, management focused on replacement heifers, especially reproductive, can contribute to achieving these goals (Abuelo et al., 2021). This work aims to present the different protocols used to induce puberty in heifers and the associated benefits for the cow as well as for the farm.

II. MAXIMIZING REPRODUCTIVE EFFICIENCY

The delay in the reproductive life of the dams has the consequences of an increase in the herd of females that are not breeding, a reduction in the efficiency of calf production, resulting in a decrease in profit and a delay in the genetic selection process. The improvement in reproductive

performance, by reducing the age at first calving (IPP) of females, has a significant impact on the productive indicators of the farm. It is therefore essential that heifers enter puberty at the earliest possible age.

A. Age at Puberty

From the reproductive point of view, puberty is defined as the manifestation of reproductive capacity (Martins et al., 2021), which occurs when an animal acquires the ability to ovulate an oocyte with the presentation of estrous behavior (Augusto *et al.*, 1997; Forde *et al.*, 2011; Martins *et al.*, 2021), with development and maintenance of a functional corpus luteum with a normal lifespan (Gonzalez-Padilla et al., 1975; de Lima et al., 2020). Given this definition, puberty can be seen as an economic indicator in beef cattle (Baruselli et al., 2018). de Lima et al. (2020) and Dyck, (1988) defines it as the beginning of reproductive activity, which is marked by changes in gonadotropin concentration and by an increase in circulating sex steroid hormones which involves a complex physiological and molecular process (Gonzalez-Padilla et al., 1975; Masello et al., 2019; Kowalik et al., 2022).

The period corresponding to the 40-60 days prior to the first ovulation is designated as pre-puberty (Cardoso et al., 2020). This phase involves the transition from one period of ovarian inactivity to another, in which the final stage of maturation of the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis and the beginning of ovulations occur (Heslin et al., 2020). For this reason, mating soon after the first estrus followed by ovulation is not advised, as fertility in this period has been reported to be low, mainly due to the occurrence of a short estrous cycle associated with premature luteolysis of the corpus luteum between the 8th and 8th. 12 days (Carvalho et al., 2008; Holland et al., 2018) resulting in a serum concentration of progesterone lower than 1.0 ng/ml on day 9 of the cycle (Côrtes et al., 2021), which prevents maintenance of pregnancy, since the critical period for the maternal recognition of the embryo occurs from the 15th to the 19th days.

The final maturation of the reproductive tract of the future mother results from exposure to ovarian steroids, from estrous cycles after puberty (Forde et al., 2011; Adams et al., 2018). Among the hormones involved in the physiology of puberty, LH is considered the primary endocrine factor for the heifer to reach puberty and this is only possible from the reduction of the negative feedback exerted by estradiol (Baruselli et al., 2018),

a phenomenon that is observed in the prepubertal phase. Pulsatile LH secretion is established in calves at around 1 to 2 months of age (Anderson et al., 1996) and increases around 3 and 5 months of age (Tsutsumi and Webster, 2009). Subsequently, LH secretion decreases and remains relatively low (static phase) until a further increase in LH secretion (prepubertal phase) culminating in puberty (Patterson et al., 1990; Anderson et al., 1996; Cardoso et al., 2020; Martins et al., 2021).

One of the causes of the increase in the frequency of LH pulses in the prepubertal phase is a consequence of the lower sensitivity of the hypothalamus to the negative feedback exerted by estradiol (Ataide Junior et al., 2021; Delchiaro et al., 2022) resulting in follicle growth antral and increased estradiol production, followed by a transient elevation in LH secretion (Dysart et al., 2021). In heifers, plasma estradiol concentration remains low until the prepubertal period, when it gradually increases until the time of the first ovulation (Codognoto et al., 2022). In addition to the changes observed in the hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal axis during the period before puberty, the sexual organs also undergo morphophysiological changes, providing adequate conditions for the establishment of pregnancy as well as an increase in the weight of the uterus, cervix and vagina, being that prepubertal heifers generally have a lower uterine diameter than pubertal heifers (Solano et al., 2000; Byrne et al., 2018; Bertogna et al., 2021).

B. Age of heifers at first calving

Management focused on age at first calving at two years of age has allowed maximizing the productive life of heifers (Lasheen et al., 2018), as those with greater sexual precocity have a longer reproductive life than late ones (Aranda -Avila, Magaña-Monforte, Segura-Correa 2010; Byrne et al. 2018; Adoligbe et al. 2020). As a result, heifers that have their first calving close to 24 months of age reach their maximum productivity (Burns et al., 2010; Ekowati et al., 2018; Cardoso et al., 2020). There are differences between *Bos indicus* and *Bos taurus* cattle in relation to the onset of puberty. In general, puberty occurs later in *Bos indicus* heifers, which is reflected in the age at first calving, which in these animals can occur at 40 months of age (Day, 2004; Cooke et al., 2021).

Factors involved in the onset of puberty include age (Martins et al., 2021), body weight (Cardoso et al., 2020) and genetic variations (Dyck, 1988; Bertogna et al., 2021). Age at puberty for Zebu heifers ranges from 22 to 36 months (González et al., 1986; Martins et al., 2021) and age at first calving between 44 and 48 months (Aranda-Avila et al., 2010; Martins et al., 2021). In taurine breeds, the first ovulation occurs between 7 and 12 months, with the first service around 15 months (Patterson et al., 1990; Hanotte et al., 2000; Cooke et al., 2021; Delchiaro et al., 2022). The Landim bovine within the Sanga group present in the Southern region of Mozambique, specifically in the provinces of Maputo, Gaza and Inhambane, widely known as Nguni (Carvalho et al., 1995; Maciel et al., 2012; King et al., 2021), in turn, is relatively earlier, which can be confirmed in the study by Carvalho et al. (1995) who studied the Landim and Africander breeds at the Chobela Research Station and obtained an age at first calving of 39.5 for Landim and 42.8 for

Africander. Maciel et al. (2012), in turn, evaluating the reproductive performance of two Nguni ecotypes (Nguni and Landim) reared in subtropical environments, found an average of 35±5 months at first calving.

Body weight affects the age of onset of puberty in cattle and its monitoring through daily weight gain control and body weight assessment is crucial as it allows predicting the onset of puberty, which makes it easy to select females that will be able to be incorporated in their first breeding season (Houghton et al., 1990; Ayres et al., 2014; D'Occhio et al., 2019; Cooke et al., 2021). In general, larger breeds are later and heavier when they reach puberty (Heslin et al., 2020). Beef heifers need to reach about 60 to 65% of their adult live weight to reach puberty (Dickinson et al., 2019). The weaning weight is essential for heifers to reach puberty and the higher the weaning weight, the better, according to the requirements of each breed, without them becoming obese, since the excess of adipose tissue in heifers during the pre-weaning can result in reduced subsequent performance of these animals (Cooke et al., 2021; Kasimanickam et al., 2021).

Genetic variations play an influence both within and between breeds and this can clearly be seen in the evaluations of age and weight effects at puberty between *Bos taurus* and *Bos indicus*. Taurine heifers generally enter at puberty between 10 - 15 months with body weight ranging from 270 - 350 kg, and calving is estimated at 24 – 26 months of age, while zebu heifers reach puberty later and with greater weight compared to adult weight, presenting an age at first calf that can reach 44 - 48 months of age (Maciel et al., 2016; Carvalho et al., 1995; Aranda-Avila et al., 2010; Figueiredo et al., 1997).

III. USE OF HORMONES ON REPRODUCTIVE EFFICIENCY

Hormones have been strategically used as a valuable alternative to increase reproductive efficiency in cattle (González et al., 1986; de Lima et al., 2020) as they allow inducing and anticipating puberty in heifers before the breeding season. (Gonzalez-Padilla et al., 1975; Carvalho et al., 2008; Martins et al., 2021). Some hormones, such as progesterone analogues (P4), administered orally (melengestrol acetate, MGA) (Patterson et al., 1990), via subcutaneous implants (norgestomet, Crestar) (González et al., 1986), or by intravaginal devices containing P4 (CIDR, DIB, PRID and SINCROGEST) (Ataide Junior et al., 2021), have been used.

Anderson et al. (1996) evaluated the mechanism by which exposure to progestins induces puberty in heifers. These results suggest that progestogens induce puberty by providing greater secretion of LH, allowing follicular growth, which results in greater production of estradiol by the ovarian follicles and LH surge, inducing ovulation and, consequently, puberty. Another mechanism involved is the decrease in hypothalamic estradiol receptors, inducing negative feedback effects of estradiol on GnRH secretion, thus enabling an increase in LH secretion (Day, 2004).

de Lima et al. (2020) evaluated the effect of puberty induction using single-dose injectable P4 on AI conception rates and found that progesterone induced a 50% increase in uterine development at 21 days and an 18% increase in follicle diameter. Assuming that progesterone has acted to make the uterus and ovaries physiologically more prepared for reproduction sooner. In addition, there was an increase of about 7.7% (iP4: 46.0% vs. NoiP4: 38.3%) in AI conception rates in the progesterone-treated heifer group. Abouel-Ghaitb (2021) studied the effect of treatments with GnRH and progesterone device (CIDR) plus eCG (1000 or 500 IU) on the induction and synchronization of puberty onset in buffalo heifers which resulted in a greater number of large follicles and rates of conception significantly higher ($P < 0.05$) than all groups and concluding that hormones can be an effective alternative for the induction and synchronization of puberty in buffaloes too.

IV. CONCLUSION

To achieve an optimal reproductive performance of cattle, it is necessary to extract maximum efficiency from each female. Heifers represent the guarantee and maintenance of production and therefore, farm management must pay special attention to this category in order to extract the maximum possible gains in the production phase and less expenses in the rearing phase. This requires each animal to have a calving every 12-13 months, with the first calving at 24 months of age and puberty entering at 14-15 months. Reproductive management in general is fundamental and hormones can represent an alternative for maximizing reproductive efficiency and obtaining greater profits, but it is the combination of several factors such as nutrition, health and genetic selection that guarantees the best results in livestock activity. Heifers that start their reproductive life earlier, produce more weaned calves during their productive life, have better reproductive rates, and therefore bring more profit to farms.

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